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Trip Attraction Models, Using Regression Analysis, for Shopping Malls in Lebanon

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ABSTRACT

The rapid increase in the number of shopping malls in Lebanon over the years necessitates proper transportation planning. The main step in the travel request process is the generation of trips. This research aims to provide travel attraction models for shopping malls in order to achieve a travel generation manual for Lebanon in the future. Seven shopping centers located in Beirut were studied, for which the number of vehicles that entered during rush hours on weekends, was gathered. In addition, the physical characteristics of the shopping centers were collected. The travel attraction rates were calculated based on the physical characteristics of the seven shopping centers. Multiple travel attraction models were generated based on the physical characteristics. Three attraction models were selected, which proved to be the most suitable for shopping malls. This study helps traffic engineers and urban planners to anticipate the impact of constructing a new shopping center in Lebanon, taking into account traffic on surrounding roads.

Introduction

A suitable transportation planning is the backbone of urban area development and the main objective of developing countries, given the fact that developing countries are facing a substantiated increase in urbanization, which subsequently necessitates proper management of Travel Demand (TD). The improvement of transportation planning relies heavily on a number of factors, such as journey time, distance, cost, comfort, and safety (Ullah and Dutta, 2017). Travel Demand is regarded as key to planning future transportation design facilities and services. In this respect, there exists a four-step model: trip generation, trip distribution, modal choice, and route assignment (Modi et al., 2011).

Trip generation is, by all means, the first stage of the TD models. For a successful long-term implementation, accuracy in this basic step is deemed necessary. Any errors in estimating the number of trips can negatively affect the entire estimation process. Trip generation is used in transportation planning to identify the number of the trip ends in a given area, from the trip origin to the destination points. In a trip generation, the planner attempts to quantify the link between activity and travel, with

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respect to Trip Production (TP) and Trip Attraction (TA) in a given Traffic Analysis Zone (TAZ) (Garrick, 2016).

Trip Production identifies the number of trips produced by households in the Traffic Analysis Zone. The factors that usually influence Trip Production are related to the household characteristics because the household is regarded as a major unit of Trip Production, such as household size, family size, number of employees in the household understudy, sexes of household individuals, household income, vehicle ownership, and ages of the persons living in the household, etc.

Trip Attraction recognizes the number of trips attracted to each activity center in the Traffic Analysis Zone. Moreover, numerous studies on TD have found that Trip Attraction has a solid correlation with land use, such as floor area, number of employees, and services (Jayasinghe, 2017). Amongst the many parameters that affect the Trip Attraction of an activity center, there is the Trip Attraction Rate (TAR), which is defined as the number of trips ends per unit time per unit of independent variables (i.e., per number of shops, per employee, per square feet of floor area, etc.). Generally, the estimation of Trip Attraction is less accurate than TP since it is hard to generate and model the parameters that affect one's choice to travel to a specific place. It is obvious that the trip generation depends on the purpose of the trip since travel behavior varies depending on the trip type. However, the primary contributing factor for Trip Attraction is work trips, and the secondary one is shopping trips.

By all means, shopping Centers (SCs) have become the centerpieces for revolutionizing cities in Lebanon; but, there is a problem that emanates from the fact that there is a lack of studies regarding the prediction of the number of shoppers that visit each Shopping Center, or when planning new ones. In this respect, regression Trip Attraction Models for SCs are very much needed in order to forecast new SCs and plan geometric design and traffic control schemes in the area that is in the proximity of the SCs.

Literature Review

Trip generation is an investigation of the relationship between the number of trips made and certain quantifiable factors. Trip generation modeling starts with the reasons that a person is traveling from an origin point to a destination point. An individual makes a trip for a reason depending on where he is going to work, shop, go to school, or any other destinations. Trips can be classified by trip purpose, trip time of the day, and personality type (Mathew and Rao, 2007). The common factors that affect trip generation are location, population intensity in the land use understudy, accessibility to residential areas, socio-economic attributes of the people living in the area, roofed space offered for commercial, industrial, and other services, and the cost and quality of transportation services (Sanghai et al., 2014).

In an effort to guide traffic and transportation engineers about trip generation rates for all land uses and building types in the United States, the Institute for Transportation Engineers (ITE) developed a Trip Generation Manual. According to ITE's Trip Generation Manual, a standard regression equation can be used for all Shopping Centers located in suburban areas and ranging in size between 1,700 and 2.2 million square feet Gross Leasable Area (GLA) (ITE Technical Council Committee, 1976). However, caution is deemed necessary when trying to extrapolate the findings to other areas of the world (Institute of Transportation Engineers, 2012).

Many types of research and studies were carried out in order to evaluate the trip generation for specific areas. In 2009, Veenstra Tutert and Thomas attempted to specify the parameters that can affect the trip generation of grocery shopping in the Netherlands. As a result, the percentages of shoppers who visited the supermarkets once a week or less was 19%, 73% for more than once per week, and 8% for daily

shoppers. They determined that the average trip rate was about 2.6 trips per shopper per week (Veenstra et al., 2009).

Another case study aimed at developing an attraction rate and providing a suitable Trip Attraction Model for seven selected Malls in Vadodara city, India (Bali & Zala, 2017). The use of a socio-economic questionnaire (primary data) helped to collect data directly from the people (primary data). In addition, other data were assembled from the municipality and Mall owners (secondary data). The parameters used were: parking spaces for two and four-wheelers, floor areas, and restaurant floor areas. As a result, the independent parameters that affected the Trip Attraction were parking space for two-wheelers and the floor area of the Shopping Mall.

Another case study in Dhaka city, Bangladesh, attempted to determine the Trip Attraction rates of Shopping Centers of different sizes and located in different locations. The calculation of Trip Attraction rates of the Shopping Centers considered physical features, such as gross floor area, number of car parking spaces, number of employees, number of shops, and availability of restaurants (available or not) in the Shopping Centers (Mamun, 2014). The survey took place over two weekdays during peak hours, from 5:00 pm to 8:00 pm. Two models were constructed, one was related to gross floor area, availability of parking spaces and restaurants, and the other one was related to the total number of shops, the availability of parking spaces, and restaurants.

Three years later, another study took place in the so-called Uttara area of Dhaka city. The aim of this study was to collect data about the number of people per unit of time who came to Shopping Centers in this area and to discuss with them the influence of many physical features on the Trip Attraction rate of the Shopping Centers located in the same zone. Six Shopping Centers were surveyed over a two-day period, on Friday and Saturday, during peak hours from 4:30 pm till 7:30 pm. The data collected over the two days were used to estimate the difference in the number of shoppers between weekdays and weekends. The collected data helped to estimate the trips per 1000 ft² per hour, the trips per shopper hour, the trips per entry gate per hour, the trips per 100 employees per hour, the trips per 10 parking spaces per hour, the peak hour car Trip Attraction rate (trips per 10,000 sq. ft. per hour) (Rahman et al., 2017).

Another study aimed at evaluating the developing shopping trip generation in a densely-populated, residential urban area, was conducted in Ahmedabad City, India. According to this study, 30.97% of the daily trips were simply for shopping purposes and 51.16% of the daily trips were for home needs (Parikh & Varia, 2016).

Methodology

A trip is a movement of an individual from one place to another. Trip Attraction signifies a trip starting or ending in a non-residential area. Before presenting the steps followed in this study, the understanding of the approach used is essential. There are two essential approaches usually used to determine the Trip Attraction model. The microscopic approach estimates the TAR of separate shops one by one then it aggregates the TAR of all the shops to have a global TAR. This idea is founded on the understanding that the SC is divided into small parts and explains its properties better than the system being measured as an entire unit. This approach was not used in this study because of the difficulty encountered in performing counts for individual shops in SCs. This method, or the so-called microscopic model, could be used in the future to compare its outcomes regarding the Trip Attraction Rates of the SC with those of the macroscopic approach.

The macroscopic approach aims to study the SC as a whole unit and develop a relationship between the number of shoppers entering or leaving the SC and the physical features of the entire SC, without getting any data about the features of the individual shops in the Shopping Center. This method is frequently used based on the idea that the characteristics of the entire system express its comportment better than considering the combination of physiognomies of the individual modules. In addition, this approach is easier to be conducted and the Trip Attraction of SCs developed in the ITE Trip Generation Manual is based on the macroscopic model. The steps that should be followed in order to succeed in this study are listed as follow: (a) Selection of the Shopping Centers for this study in the Beirut urban area. (b) Collection of the required data for the characteristics of each Shopping Center and the total number of visitors entering or leaving a Shopping Center in peak hours from 10 am till 12 pm and from 4 pm till 6 pm on weekends for the seven Malls. (c) Trip Attraction Rates should be computed based on each physical feature. (d) Selection of the three best-fit Trip Attraction Models for Shopping Centers in Lebanon using statistical methods.

Data Collection

The Trip Attraction Rate of a Shopping Center was gained by counting the number of shoppers entering and leaving the SC for every 15 minutes interval. The number of visitors entering each SC was counted for an hour, then the average of the Trip Attraction Rate for every 15 minutes was calculated. As a first step, an investigation and statistical data collection for ABC Ashrafieh was conducted for complete weekdays from Monday to Sunday from 10:00 until 23:00. Those records were used to verify the peak hours that should be selected for this study in order to get the highest number of shoppers that could enter the SC and illustrate the variation in the number of visitors between weekdays and weekends.

The peak typical time for shopping during weekdays is after work exactly from 4:00 pm to 7:00 pm according to the statistics. Usually, Fridays attract more visitors than other weekdays. In addition, Saturdays and Sundays are the most used two days for shopping. It is obviously clear that the counts are logical in Figure 1. The counts for all of the Shopping Centers have to be conducted during weekends, also during peak hours that coincide with the surrounding traffic during the day from 10:00 am until 12:00 pm and 4:00 pm until 6:00 pm. In addition, the physical features for each Shopping Centre have been collected and tabulated in Table 1.

Figure 1. Variation of counts between weekend and weekdays

Table 1. Characteristics and average 15 minutes Trip Attraction for Shopping Centers

Shopping Centers	ABC Ashrafieh	ABC Dbayeh	ABC Verdun	City Center	CityMall	Le Mall Dbayeh	Le Mall Sin El Fil
GLA (m ²)	42000	24095	50000	62000	80000	25000	12000
Number of Shops	170	100	180	179	220	77	80
Number of Restaurants & Cafes	20	12	20	40	31	27	11
Number of Employees	1000	800	1100	1620	1552	640	400
Cinema	2600	2900	3757	5000	4500	3000	0
Playground Area	629	740	1600	2500	4000	500	380
Number of parking	1300	1100	1700	2200	2500	1500	700
Free Parking	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Free Wifi	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Supermarket	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
TA for 15 mins	94	72	95	145	136.73	59.82	29.05

Analysis and Results

Trip Attraction Rates

The Trip Attractions Rate of a Shopping Center is influenced by a number of features, like the time of day, day of the week either during weekend or weekday, season, weather, etc. The Trip Attraction Rate evaluated in this study is related to weekend peak hours. The number of people entering the SC every 15 minutes interval for one hour at an entrance gate was counted. The data collected and the average Trip Attraction for 15 minutes are shown in Table 1. TAR was computed with respect to diverse physical features, as person trips/1000 m²/hour, person trips/100 employees/hour, person trips/restaurant/hour, person trips/shop/hour, and person trips/10 parking spaces/hour, etc. In order to estimate the influence of each physical feature according to SCs, the different TAR is computed accordingly.

Gross Leasable Area (GLA)

The equation used for the calculation of the peak hour person TAR per 1000 m² GLA is represented in "Eq.1". According to the results in Figure 2, the highest peak hour person TAR is in ABC Dbayeh with 11.95 person trip per 1000 m² per hour. This Mall attracts the highest number of person trips per hour per 1000 m² GLA because it is a popular Shopping Center with unique branded shops. The second highest value is 9.68 persons/1000 m²/hour for the CityCenter. This Mall is popular because of its strategic location in the Beirut Area. The lowest peak hour person TAR corresponds to ABC Verdun with approximately 7.6 person trips/1000 m² GLA/hour. This Mall has the same unique brand shops but it opened recently in 2017 and it is not as popular. In addition, a grand average of 9.14 person trips/1000 m² GLA/hour was calculated with a Standard Deviation (SD) of 1.52 for the seven Shopping Centers.

$$\text{Trips per 1000 m}^2 \text{ per hour} = \text{Peak hour person trip} / \text{GLA} \times 1000$$

[1]

Figure 2. Person trips per 1000 m² GLA per hour

Number of Employees

The equation used for the calculation of person trips/100 employees/hour is given by “Eq.2”. In addition, Figure 3 depicts the peak hour TAR/employee/hour for the seven Shopping Centers. It seems that the variation is limited. Overall, an average of 34.18 person trips/100 employees/hour was determined for the Shopping Centers under study, with a standard deviation of 3.62.

Trips per 100 employee/hour = Peak hour person trip/Employees x 100 [2]

Figure 3. Person trips per 100 employee per hour

Number of Shops and Restaurants

The equations used for the calculation of person trips/store/hour are given by “Eq.3” and by “Eq.4” for person trips/restaurant/hour. Figure 4 shows the variation in TAR in relation to the shops and restaurants. It is clear that person trips/restaurant/hour is higher than person trips/shop/hour. The variation is understandable given that a restaurant attracts more persons in one hour than a shop. Overall, an average of 2.35 person trips/shop/hour and 16.2 person trips/restaurant/hour were predicted for the Shopping Centers in the Beirut urban area, with standard deviations of 0.6 and 4.87, respectively.

Trips per store per hour = Peak hour person trip / No. of Stores [3]

Trips per restaurant per hour = Peak hour person trip / No. of Restaurants [4]

Figure 4: Person trips per store and restaurant per hour

Number of parking spaces

The determination of person trips/10 parking spaces/hour is based on “Eq.5”. According to Figure 5, the highest peak hour person TAR is in ABC Achrafieh, with 2.89 person trips/10 parking spaces/hour. The lowest peak hour person trips/10 parking spaces/hour correspond to Le Mall Dbayeh, with approximately 1.6 person trips/10 parking spaces/hour. Overall, an average of 2.26 person trips/10 parking spaces/hour, with a standard deviation of 0.46, was found.

Trips per parking per hour = Peak hour person trip/No. of parkings × 10 [5]

Figure 5. Person trips per 10 parking space per hour

Cinema and playground

Person trips/10 m² cinema/hour are based on “Eq.6”, and person trips/10 m² playground/hour are based on “Eq.7”. Figure 6 depicts the variation in TAR, as a function of the physical cinema and playground features. It is clear that person trips/10 m² playground/hour is higher than person trips/10 m² cinema/hour. It can be concluded that a Shopping Center attracts a higher number of visitors/hour/10 m² playground, as compared to person trips/hour/ 10 m² cinema. Overall, an average of 1.16 person trips/10 m² cinema/hour and 3.4 person trips/10 m² playground/hour were predicted for the Shopping Centers in the Beirut urban area, with standard deviations of 1.01 and 1.48, respectively.

Trips per 10 m² cinema per hour = Peak hour person trip/Cinema × 10 [6]
Trips per 10 m² playground per hour = Peak hour person trip/playground × 10 [7]

Figure 6. Person trips per 10 m² cinema & 10 m² playground per hour

Correlation and Regression Analysis

Correlation and regression analysis are linked by the concept of the relationships between variables. The correlation coefficient describes the strength of the linear relationship between variables. As can be deduced from the following correlation table, using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), that there is a very high positive relationship between Trip Attraction per 15 min and GLA, which is statistically significant at α=0.05 [r(6) = 0.945, p<0.05].

Table 2: Correlation between Trip Attraction per 15 min and the independent variables

Variables	GLA (m ²)	Shops Number	Restaurants Number	Employees Number	Cinema	Kids Area	Parking spaces	SuperMarket	Free Parking	Free Wifi
Correlation	0.945	0.885	0.81	0.996	0.91	0.874	0.915	0.84	- 0.759	0.67

It can be concluded from Table 2 that the correlation between Trip Attraction and the other variables is a positive one. In other words, when the variables under study increase, Trip Attraction increases too. The only variable that seems to negatively affect Trip Attraction is the availability of free parking spaces. In general, when parking spaces are free, the Shopping Center should be able to attract more trips; unfortunately, this is not the case in Lebanon. Although there is free parking in Le Mall Dbayeh and Le Mall Sin El Fil, they attract trips much lower than other Malls due to a number of factors, among which their small GLA, the availability of a Super Market, etc.

Regression Models

The aim of this section is to come up with the best non-linear regression models to describe Trip Attraction, as a function of several independent variables.

- Using exponential regression analysis, the Trip Attraction model of SC, as a function of the number of employees, is represented by “Eq.8”, where X1 is the number of employees and Y is the average Trip Attraction of a Shopping Center with respect to the number of vehicles per 15 mins. This model seems to be the best regression equation since the value of the coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.992.

Y = e^{(1.007 ln(X₁)-2.693)} [8]

- The Trip Attraction equation of the SC, as based on the number of shops and restaurants (see “Eq. 9”), where X2 is the number of shops, X3 is the number of restaurants, and Y is the average Trip Attraction of a Shopping Center with respect to the number of vehicles per 15 mins. It should be noted that the number of shops and the number of restaurants are not collinear since the Variance Inflation Factor $VIF = 1.46$ is below 10, meaning that the two variables could be included in the same regression equation. The value of R^2 is 0.927, meaning that 92.7% of the variation in Trip Attraction are explained by the non-linear regression equation containing the number of shops and the number of restaurants.

$$Y = e^{(0.67 \ln(X_2) + 0.505 \ln(X_3) - 0.625)} \tag{9}$$

- The Trip Attraction model of the SC, as a function of 1000 m² GLA, is represented by the exponential regression equation “Eq.10”, where X1 is the Gross Leasable Area per 1000 m² and Y is the average Trip Attraction of a Shopping Center with respect to the number of vehicles per 15 mins. The sign of X4 is positive as expected since the Trip Attraction seems to increase when the GLA for an SC increases. The value of R^2 is 0.912, indicating that 91.2% of the total variation in Trip Attraction is explained by the non-linear regression equation containing the Gross Leasable Area per 1000 m².

$$Y = e^{(0.719 \ln(X_4) + 1.622)} \tag{10}$$

The regression models 8 to 10, as functions of physical features of GLA, employees count, and the number of shops and restaurants at the six SC in the Beirut urban area, are depicted in Figure 7 against the observed TA.

Figure 7. Variation between the Trip Attraction regression models and the Trip Attraction observed for the six SC in the Beirut urban area

Conclusion and Recommendations

Trip generation is the main step in the four-step trip modeling process. It encompasses both the attraction of travel and the production of travel by estimating the number of journeys made per unit of time, whether entering or exiting a particular traffic analysis zone, as a function of socio-economic characteristics and land use characteristics.

The aim of this study was to collect data on the number of visitors to SCs in seven shopping centers in an urban area of Beirut and to generate models for estimating the TARs of the SCs. The models could be used for planning and designing SCs, as well as for the geometric design features and traffic control schemes on the streets that are in close proximity to SCs. A series of surveys and data collection were conducted to obtain peak-hour counts and to determine the physical features of SCs, in order to estimate Trip Attraction Models for SC. The TAR per each physical feature was computed and the Trip Attraction Models based on SC characteristics were produced based on each physical feature. The three best Trip Attraction Models were selected according to R^2 values. It was concluded that the Gross Leasable Area, number of employees, and number of shops and restaurants were the main physical features that influence the number of trips to SCs. After calculating the Trip Attraction Models, a comparison was made between the average TAR value assessed in Lebanon and other countries like the US, Saudi Arabia, Abu Dhabi, and Dubai.

Trip generation models are recommended for other activity centers during peak morning and afternoon hours, on weekends and weekdays, in order to improve the modeling of traffic flows in the future for better transport planning processes in Lebanon. Researchers are asked to study similar models for other Shopping Centers in Lebanon and check their validity. Additionally, officials and planners can use the results of the trip generation models presented in this study to estimate the number of shoppers that would visit a new Shopping Center in Lebanon. The same test could be done on weekdays to compare the results with the weekends. Finally, researchers are asked to collect a new data set in the future and apply the new data in the models developed in this study to ensure that the models will continue to be valid in the future, by comparing the estimated trips of the developed models with observed trips.

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